

DIGITAL ADVERTISING: FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PURCHASE INTENTION OF FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOODS

Chakkaravarthy kumaresan R Research Scholar, Alagappa Institute of Management, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India: cskumaresan.mech@gmail.com

Dr.S.Chandramohan Professor, Alagappa Institute of Management, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

Today's Commercial scenario is occupied by digital advertising. Success of a effective advertisement remains main guiding feature aimed at consumption activities. Modern business people are spending additional cost as well as extra time for online advertising have been found to be highly effective in building customer engagement, an element that determines the prevalence of consumers' purchase intention of Fast Moving Consumer Goods. Day by Day technology is getting innovative, people be getting hooked more towards internet, they be in a situation to spent most time in Accessible watching favourites, in instead particular interval tend to see frequent advertisements, explore time in advertisements unknowingly. This paper reports on recent enquiry undertaken overall Madurai per a sample size of 200 respondents. A investigation scrutiny was developed situate on the literature study, the question sheet were analysed quantitatively using reliability analysis. The collected data were analysed using Descriptive Analysis, ANOVA, Rank analysis as statistical tools. This research primarily aims to determine the digital advertising specifically social media and email marketing on purchase intention.

Keywords: *Digital advertising, Social media, Fast Moving Consumer Goods, Purchaseintention*

INTRODUCTION

Digital advertising is promotional material delivered to a target audience through digital platforms, including social media, email, search engines, mobile apps, affiliate programs, and websites. One of the main benefits of digital advertising is an advertiser can track in real time the success of the campaign. The goal of digital advertising is to inorganically advertise where consumers are and to customize ads to the target audience's preferences. Purchase intentions are a very important metric in marketing. In fact, marketing based on intentions or intent marketing is about marketing goods & items based on the intentions of the consumers or the consumer's intent to accept, buy or use a particular product or service which may or may not have been clearly mentioned by the company or brand. Purchase intentions as a measurement are effective in designing marketing activities or promotions. The intent of a customer can make it very easy to exactly iterate what kind of content should be displayed in an advertisement. The intentions can reflect information about the knowledge levels of the consumer's mind. And on the basis of this measurement the design of marketing activities can be formed. Purchase intentions of a customer base can be analyzed to make an integrated map of how to go about an advertising campaign.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

- Understanding the new marketing strategies for relationship building in the current digital Advertising
- Engagement being the key to building relationships, thus exploring the channels providing conducive environment for engaging customers
- After studying the consumer purchase intention journey through insights with respect to new parameters, marketers need to revise strategy, media spend and other organizational roles.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the factors Influencing Purchase intention of Fast Moving Consumer Goods through digital Advertising.

- To analyze the significant difference between age and digital advertising

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Digital advertising as a move toward data-driven marketing communication, the impact of artificial intelligence on advertisement production, and the effect of big data on advertisement execution. In the context of these trends, six propositions are posited concerning the management of future digital advertising and the methods and systems for delivering targeted advertisements to consumers. **Heejun Lee & Chang-Hoan Cho (2019)**, Purchase intention usually is related to the behavior, perceptions and attitudes of consumers. Purchase behavior is a key point for consumers to access and evaluate the specific product. **Vahidreza Mirabi & Hamid Akbariyeh (2015)** Purchase intention is the preference of consumer to buy the product or service. In another words, purchase intention has another aspect that the consumer will purchase a product after evaluation. Many factors affect the consumer's intention while selecting the product and the ultimate decision depends on consumers' intention with large external factors (**Keller, 2001**). Respondents are having more or less similar mind-set with respect to recommending the brand through various channels, wherein the social networking sites and Word-of-Mouth are found to be mostly used, which doesn't entail any marketing cost for the marketers. **Gupta, P., & Singh, S. (2010)**. The convergence of the Internet and wireless telecommunications in the late 1990s has opened the way for a plethora of data services for the mobile handset user. One potential area of development is wireless advertising. **Barnes, S. J. (2002)**.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study is both descriptive and analytical in nature, mainly based on the purchase intention about FMCGs. This study carried out observation and survey questioning methods, which are attributes of descriptive research. Convenience sampling technique is adopted for individual contact from sample respondents of FMCGs Consumer and also due to time constraint convenience sample was followed. The sample size is 200 respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS**Table 1: Demographic Variables of Fast moving consumer Goods**

SI.No.	Factors	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	112	56.4
		Female	88	43.6
2	Age	Below 25	41	20.5
		25 – 35	56	28
		36 – 45	49	24.5
		46- 55	54	27
3	Marital Status	Married	113	56.5
		Unmarried	87	43.5
4	Education	Student	24	12
		UG/Diploma	82	41
		PG	66	33
		Others	28	14
5	Family income per month	<20,000	28	14
		21,000-40,000	70	35
		41000-60000	65	32.5
		Above 60,000	37	18.5

6	Time spent in Advertising	Less than 15 mts	110	55
		15mts- 30mts	78	39
		Above 30mts	12	6

Source: Primary Data

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are summarized in table 1. Out of 200 respondents, 56.4% of the respondents were male and the remaining 44.6% were female. 28% of an employee falls under the age group of 25 – 35 Years and 56.5% of respondents were married, 41% of the respondents are the education qualification of UG/Diploma, 32.5% of the respondents are fall under the family income per month are 41,000-60,000. Majority of the respondents 55% spent time in Advertising less than 15 minutes.

Table 2: Kendall’s Coefficient Concordance and Mean Rank Digital Advertising

Variables	Mean Rank	
Website/Technology	5.47	
Product categories	5.24	
Ease of Use	5.30	
Mode and speed of delivery of the product	5.38	
Payment options	5.34	
Price of the product	5.62	
Design of the product	5.18	
Quality and availability of the product	6.13	
Offer (product, service on sale)	5.76	
Shipping, return and exchange policies	5.60	
Kendall’s	W. Value	Table value
	0.009	0.4

Source: primary data

Table -2 interpreted the Kendall’s Coefficient Concordance test was used to test their similarities towards the digital advertising in assigning the ranks with the coefficient rank. Quality and availability of the product were ranked first in the present study. Since the calculated value is 0.009 to compare with table value is 0.4 it is concluding that there are no similarities among the digital advertising normally as low.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGE AND PURCHASE INTENTION

H₀: There is no significant difference between age and Purchase Intention

Table 3 : Relationship between age and Purchase Intention

Particulars		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Hypothesis (Accepted/ Rejected)
Attitude	Between Groups	692	3	.231	.126	.945	Accepted
	Within Groups	323.369	176	1.837			
	Total	324.061	179				
Buying impulse	Between	3.098	3	1.033	1.244	.295	Accepted

	Groups						
	Within Groups	146.102	176	.830			
	Total	149.200	179				
Subjective norms	Between Groups	1.635	3	.545	.455	.714	Accepted
	Within Groups	210.915	176	1.198			
	Total	212.550	179				
Brand Image	Between Groups	11.156	3	3.719	3.206	.025	Accepted
	Within Groups	204.155	176	1.160			
	Total	215.311	179				
Self-efficacy	Between Groups	5.769	3	1.923	1.599	.191	Accepted
	Within Groups	211.625	176	1.202			
	Total	217.394	179				
Country of origin Image	Between Groups	8.888	3	2.963	1.891	.133	Accepted
	Within Groups	275.757	176	1.567			
	Total	284.644	179				
Interaction	Between Groups	2.846	3	.949	.600	.616	Accepted
	Within Groups	278.132	176	1.580			
	Total	280.978	179				
Accessibility	Between Groups	2.397	3	.790	.291	.832	Accepted
	Within Groups	234.514	176	1.332			
	Total	236.911	179				
Comment posting	Between Groups	1.194	3	.398	.407	.748	Accepted
	Within Groups	240.467	176	1.366			
	Total	241.661	179				
Content Usefulness	Between Groups	2.006	3	.669	.869	.458	Accepted
	Within Groups	288.944	176	1.642			
	Total	290.950	179				
Sharing /Friends Likes	Between Groups	3.793	3	1.264	1.430	.236	Accepted
	Within Groups	256.118	176	1.455			

	Total	259.911	179			
--	-------	---------	-----	--	--	--

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 one –way ANOVA was applied to test the significant difference between factors of using the Purchase intention and age. The calculated value of Brand Image 3.206, the significant value was .025, and hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

The calculated value of Attitude .126, the significant value was .945. The calculated value of Buying impulse.1.244, the significant value was .295. The calculated value of Subjective norms. 455, the significant value was .714. The calculated value of Self- efficacy.1, 599, significant value was .191. The calculated value for Country of origin Image.1.891, the significant value was .133. The calculated value of Interaction .600, the significant value was .616. The calculated value of Accessibility.291, the significant value was .832. The calculated value Comment posting.407, the significant value was .748. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. The calculated value of Content Usefulness .869, the significant value was.458. The calculated value of Sharing /Friends Likes 1.430, the significant value was.236. There is a significant relationship between the Purchase intention and age.

CONCLUSION

For many FMCG marketers, digital campaign success still has to be measured via proxies which include metrics as diverse as demographic reach, ad view ability, video completion and click through rates. Brands need to revise the strategy with respect to the experience and the value they are giving to the consumers. E-marketers have to build a strong presence in order to give a worthy experience as this is what the consumers are expecting from the brand. They have to focus on the emotional aspect rather than the rational benefits so that consumers repurchase the brand. Utilization of social networking sites and word of mouth is having high advocacy rates so marketers need to focus more on these channels in order to get competitive advantage.

REFERENCES

1. Mirabi, V., Akbariyeh, H., & Tahmasebifard, H. (2015). A study of factors affecting on customers purchase intention. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology (JMEST)*, 2(1).
2. Younus, S., Rasheed, F., & Zia, A. (2015). Identifying the factors affecting customer purchase intention. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*.
3. Lee, H., & Cho, C. H. (2020). Digital advertising: present and future prospects. *International Journal of Advertising*, 39(3), 332-341.
4. Priya, Rama & Premnath, Sudhamathi. (2019). Factors Influencing Effectiveness of Online Advertisement towards Consumer Purchase Decision. 10.35940/ijrte.B1134.0782S619.
5. Gupta, P., & Singh, S. (2010). Brand advocacy and brand bonding: New parameters in consumer purchase decision journey in the digital world. *Harvard Business Review*.
6. Barnes, S. J. (2002). Wireless digital advertising: nature and implications. *International journal of advertising*, 21(3), 399-420.